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THE LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC COMPARATIVENESS OF
LANGUAGES IN LINGUISTIC TRANSLATION

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Abstract: *The work consists of literary translation contained theoretical and practical recommendations for the study of stylistic coloring issues, strategies for the translation of stylistic devices and expressive means. The theoretical significance contributes to the further development of comparative linguistic and stylistic analysis of the original literary work intended for the general reader and its translation, defining the main stylistic peculiarities typical for works of the mass literature. The research work also set conditions for further development of methods of complex stylistic analysis of literary unit original text in translation.*

Keywords: *stylistic approaches, extra-linguistics, culture-specific words, national color, phraseological words, linguacultural words, socio-linguistic approach.*

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ЛИНГВОСТИЛИСТИЧЕСКАЯ СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ЯЗЫКОВ В
ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОМ ПЕРЕВОДЕ

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Аннотация: *Это работа состоит из художественного перевода, содержит теоретические и практические рекомендации по изучению вопросов стилистического колорита, стратегии перевода стилистических приемов и выразительных средств. Теоретическая значимость способствует дальнейшему развитию сопоставительного лингвостилистического анализа оригинального художественного произведения, предназначенного для массового читателя, и его перевода, определяющего основные стилистические особенности, характерные для произведений массовой литературы. В ходе исследования также были созданы условия для дальнейшего развития методов комплексного стилистического анализа художественной единицы исходного текста в переводе.*

Ключевые слова: *стилистические подходы, экстра-лингвистика, оснащённые культурные слова, национальный калорит, фразеологизмы, языка-культурные слова, социо-языковые подходы.*

LINGVISTIK TARJIMADA TILLARNING LINGVISTIK VA STILISTIK QIYOSLANISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola stilistik rang berish masalalarini, stilistik vositalar va ekspressiv vositalarni tarjima qilish strategiyalarini o'rganish bo'yicha nazariy va amaliy tavsiyalarni o'z ichiga olgan badiiy tarjimadan iborat. Nazariy ahamiyati keng o'quvchi uchun mo'ljallangan asl adabiy asarning qiyosiy lingvistik-stilistik tahlilini va uning tarjimasini yanada rivojlantirishga, ommaviy adabiyot asarlariga xos bo'lgan asosiy stilistik xususiyatlarni belgilashga xizmat qiladi. Tadqiqot ishi tarjimada adabiy birlikning asl matnini kompleks stilistik tahlil qilish usullarini yanada rivojlantirish uchun ham shart-sharoitlarni belgilab berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: uslubiy yondashuvlar, ekstra-lingvistika, madaniyatga bog'liq so'zlar, milliy bo'yoqdorlik, frazeologizmlar, lingvomadaniy so'zlar, ijtimoiy-lingvistik yondashuvlar.

Introduction

The co-relation of stylistic units along with the extra-linguistic approaches can be occurred in the context through the national color and cultural-specific words that are peculiared to the origin language. Every stylistic devices and expressive means can be formed in a base of linguacultural, phraseological and socio-cultural words which specify the national features of source literary text. Referring to the background knowledge the translator has to convey the meaning of culture-specific words, preserving their usages into target language. The translator pays an attention how to transmit these stylistically bounded words, whether preserving the stylistic or rather an extra-linguistic patterns. But, the translation process refers to the second one through the first which is necessary for recipients to understand the national color. In this case, the stylistic units play a role of mediator in the expression of subsequent cultural words.

Methods and materials

The linguistic translation is a subject, which studies the different aspects and peculiarities of the languages, both the origin and translating languages. The process is usually carried out through the comparison of two languages' units and norms. The aspects of linguistic norms lay on interlingual linguistic peculiarities, that includes the grammatical, lexical, stylistic, phraseological utterances, specifically to the certain language. The essence of the linguistic standards and norms can be sufficient for each language, where it had been built in language routine itself. And the subject of linguistic translation explores the diversity and identity of these aspects between two languages. It may put them for the overview, discussion, identifying the similarities, and making the decisions.

Basically, if researcher looks back for the history and origin of the languages, particularly the time of appearance of the language, it shows the linguistic identity and similarity, while the languages belong to the same class of language family. Likely, Latin languages' family, German languages, Slovenian languages' families, whereby the linguists can find the identity and similarity between the languages, in which family they belong. Apparently, while the translators deal with the transmission of the text, they come cross less difficulties in languages' structures, as they have been built in the same parallel construction. For the occasion of conveying the translation in this case from one language to another, the other extra-linguistic norms, phraseological and stylistic approaches may be the most important aspects for delivering the information, that occurred in the origin language. Contradictorily, the languages which do not belong to the same languages' family, will challenge the translators to translate the texts, especially the literary texts, where the linguistic patterns and similarities are not crossed together. The work includes the comparativeness between Uzbek and English languages, that belong to the different families of a language.

Languages which have the various grammatical structures, word formation, dialect, pronunciation, lexicon and stylistics. It has to be mentioned, that the Uzbek is rendered in a base of Turkish languages, while the English is relevant to the German languages' family. The major discussion and overview can be seen in literary texts' translation in linguistic translation. As J. Vinay and J. Darbelnet says that "Since the available linguistic expression forms never quite exhaust the potential items to be named, it is not surprising that they are rarely the same in both languages. Each source language has its gaps, which are not necessarily the same as those of the target language. Translators must be aware of the fact that in the source language there are words which do not have a match in the target language. The signified may not exist or not be acknowledged in one of the two languages; or it may exist in both but is only named independently in one of them" [10, 65]. Overall, it gives the translators to think about and how to avoid any misunderstandings, while the translation process is being carried out. Literary translation is an art, the transmission of source literary text units to the target text deals with both interlingual approaches. The perception of the meaning into target language refers the linguistic, lexical, stylistic approaches, and how they convey into translating language, the process of preservation semantic property of original material into target language units. The literary text is guided as a complicated process to understand it is demanded an effort of translator. As G. Watson and S. Zingier mentioned: "Processing of literary text is often seen as difficult, but also worth the effort as a potentially rich and engaging source of relevant language data from which to learn" [12, 4]. Thus, the literary text in source language has variant and complicated substitutes in target language that is vary the collaboration and at the same time involves the relevant features between two languages. As it regarded also in E. Black research works "It is to be expected that literary discourse will differ from ordinary conversation and some written discourse since any published work is subject to a process of careful composition and much revision" [1,3]. One of the main points of literary translation in linguistic translation is its stylistic peculiarities which play the most important role to demonstrate the literature as a whole heritage of a nation in a certain language and the style of the author.

The Stylistic discourse is included the multi-functionality of the usages of the stylistic devices and expressive means in order to create the emotionality of the context in literary texts. The author's style, that has been already existed in the literal prose can be determined through the chosen stylistic properties of a language. It says also in P. Simpson's overview that "Moreover, stylistics often forms a core component of many creative writing courses, an application not surprising given the discipline's emphasis on techniques of creativity and invention in language" [7, 2]. Accordingly, the author conveys those emotions in the context by evaluating the stylistic approaches of the utterances which can be held through the extra-linguistic and linguistic proposals of the source language. Thus, the translation process demands a lot of efforts to preserve this semantic uniqueness, while the work is transmitting from source language into target language.

Apparently, the stylistics of each languages is an own property of the creator or author. Regarding K. Wales classification "While the term style is often associated with the distinctive way an individual use the language, an equally common approach is to categorize styles as types of discourse used by a group or groups of people and deriving from the functions of language, i.e. various types of language used in specific situations. Style may also refer to wide categories such as written and spoken language, or fact and fiction, or these main categories may be divided into subcategories depending on the purpose the language is used for in each case. What is common to all these descriptions of style is that there is always a situational context to which the lots of varieties of style are linked" [11, 26]. The origin text stylistic devices and expressive means will not be identity to that one which is occurred in target language. Basically, it is relevant with the language's linguistic and extra-linguistic patterns, which are peculiar for the certain language representatives. It is important to determine them especially within context, approaching the general overviews of the given stylistic units from inside of national color. J. Boase Beier reviews "various stylistically-oriented approaches had been applied as far back as the cultures of antiquity, though these style-related characterizations may have used other terms to refer to the stylistic aspects of a text, such as the spirit of the text" [2, 6].

Results and Discussions

The main objection of source text components translating into target language should confirm the preservation of compound meanings of both literary texts, in source language and target language. The stylistic devices and expressive means in this role have to be taken into the consideration of semantic value. Thus, to find out an equivalence in target language consider as a main purpose of translator. Furthermore, in some cases, in order to preserve the whole content semantic value, the stylistic devices in source text can be transmitted by sub-equivalence or replaced by target language readers' familiar words neutralized in the content.

So, the equivalence method plays a significant role to contribute the source language's linguistic and stylistic aspects into target language through evaluating the meaning according to the content. Overall "equivalency is the semantic similarity between source text and target text, it has the role of catalysator in the process of translation" [13, 57]. It has to mention that through this method of translation, the process may involve the diverse perception in both

languages. But, there are some similarities where the elements and structures in source material would be fully preserved in translating language. It can be identified by comparison of two languages. “The functionality of equivalency is different from other points of view, as the conception of equivalency determines out of comparison source and target text, for the functionality of equivalency comes out from comparison of external lingual reaction of these texts” [14, 19]. So, the concept evaluates the extra-linguistic factors of two languages, which focused to define the concrete attitude towards the conveying the exact semantics of translating resources, avoiding any ambiguities of word combinations or set expressions that rendered the stylistic units of a language within context. Eventually, the created work and literature, the style used by author may influence the whole value of this conception, which the translation process precedes to adopt this theory in practice as per language organizing. As per M. Tolan “Looking at the technique or craft of writing, language in literature examines the way which language is organized to create literary effect and meaning” [8, 13]. Accordingly, writing style may contribute the overall linguistic and extra-linguistic patterns in the content. The translator renders the meaning into target language through the equivalency methods which are specific for contribution of linguistic and stylistic units. So, we consider them through the comparison of two languages.

For example:

“*Dadam bilan oyim: -Oyog’ing olti, qo’ling yetti bo’lib qoldiyov!- deb kulishib goldilar*” [16, 5].

In English:

“*-You are hurrying like you have six legs and seven hands. -laughed my parents*” [author’s translation].

“*Quyushqoni ham o’rnida, egar ham yaxshi qo’ngan, qorinbog’i ham jips, yugan ham to’ralarnikidek!*” [16, 6].

“*The crupper was perfect. The saddle was firm. The girth was tight. And the bridle was as proper as officials*” [author’s translation].

“*O’sha kuni terdik. Uyat o’limdan qattiq.... El qatori terdim*” [15, 18].

“*That day we picked cotton, because shame is worse than death*” [author’s translation].

“*Ba’zan egatlar ichida tarvuz, qovun palaklari chiqib qolardi. Albatta, bitta-ikkita burishgan, tirishgan tuynak bo’lardi. Ammo uni yorib yesangiz, mazasi.... tilni yoradi*” [15, 18].

“*Sometimes we saw melon and water-melon lashes in the furrows. Of course, there were one or two green, wrinkled fruits, but if you broke and ate it would crack your tongue*” [author’s translation].

As here one can observe that the used stylistic devices and expressive means in the source content is fully preserved their form and meaning into target language, considering that they have complete correspondence in translating language. Consequently, the same hyperbole, repetition, paradox and metonymy which have been used in the source context can be found and widely classified in English. For the such kind of equivalence translation we come cross with V.N. Komissarov’s theory of translation, in which it states: the fifth type of equivalency method supposes for the preservation of stylistic characteristics of source units during

translation. It denotes, that it is compulsory to preserve any stylistic units within context in target language, if this language has the same linguistic and stylistic patterns in the language barriers. The same procedures might be overviewed in translation of literary context from English into Uzbek.

For example:

“Her **heart was divided** between **concern** for her sister, **and resentment** against all others” [6, 167].

“Uning qalbi opasiga nisbatan **tashvish** va boshqalarga qarshi **g‘azabga to‘lgan edi**” [author’s translation].

“Today **we love** what tomorrow **we hate**; today **we seek** what tomorrow **we shun**” [5, 201].

“Bugun **suyukli** bo‘lgan narsa, ertaga **yoqimsiz** bo‘lishi, **izlanayotgan** narsa **yo‘qotilishi** mumkin” [author’s translation].

“**How do I know** what God himself judges in this particular case?” [5, 220].

“Xususan, bu holatda Oloh hukmini **qayerdan ham biladi kishi?**” [author’s translation].

“**Malone laughed a horse-laugh**” [4, 17].

“**Malon ot hurkish kulimsirab qo‘ydi**” [author’s translation].

““Forward” was the device stamped upon his soul; but **poverty curbed him**” [4, 28].

“Faqat “olg‘a” degan so‘z uning qalbida muhrlangan edi; ammo **qashshoqlik bunga yo‘l qo‘ymas edi**” [author’s translation].

“A **man** almost without sympathy, ungentle, prejudiced, and rigid; **but a man true to principle- honorable, sagacious, and sincere**” [4, 36].

“O‘z navbatida deyarli hamdardliksiz, qo‘pol, gap uqtirmas **inson** bo‘lishiga qaramasdan, tamoyillarga sodiq, sharaflı, bilimlı va samimiy **shaxs** ham edi” [author’s translation].

“It was **curious laugh**; distinct, formal, mirthless” [7, 163].

“Bu **qiziqqon kulgi** edi; o‘ziga xos, jiddiy, vahimalarsiz” [author’s translation].

“The text has two main interconnected text-forming functions: the impact function and aesthetic” [9, 24]. While the translator deals with the translation to the target language he or she must follow the exact preservation of these functions, in order to convey the perception to the target language recipients. It is important to highlight that the literary texts are rich in aesthetic features, which contribute the emotions and impressiveness to readers. Accordingly, stylistic meaning carries these peculiarities to fulfill the masterpiece work in literary art. Thus, evaluating this meaning to the translating language is highly connected with the equivalence in translation.

Conclusion

There has been calculated several views of different linguists and translators in an address of linguistic and stylistic unit translation from one language into another in literary texts, that some views and theories are cross-referenced to each other, and others are contradictorily suggested in a theory of linguistic translation. Some aspects have already

proved that stylistic units are the set expressions which are formed in a base of relevant linguacultural or socio-lingual approaches, as they peculiar for the certain national phenomenon. Phraseological units regarded as the unique set expressions, which the phraseological meaning is obtained as the whole semantics without non-segmented elements may refer the units of stylistics in a foundation of any phraseological categories within content. That's why the translators' main role in this case is to acknowledge with the origin and usages of such kind of stylistic units, formed in a base of these abovementioned major aspects of the language. Stylistics is the discourse which reflects the national coloring and evaluation of the meanings, fulfilling with impressiveness within context in literary text. It gives the vast opportunities for the authors and literary work creators to approach with different attitudes for the selecting of word collocations, expressions, that serve for the exaggerating of national coloring.

The matter includes the conclusion to the perception of translation of stylistic devices and expressive means into foreign language through the distinction of both language units, linguistic, extra-linguistic and stylistic aspects. The main criteria, the term of equivalence in translation is regarded as a specific, multi-functional approach which has been chosen in transmission of stylistic units as proper equivalent, sub-equivalent and non-equivalent or descriptive-neutral method of conveying the perception of stylistic devices into translating language.

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